

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society programme under grant agreement no. 872483

Project acronym:

DocEnhance

Project title:

“Enhancing skills intelligence and integration into existing PhD programmes by providing transferable skills training through an open online platform”

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² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specifies by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Revision History			
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0.1	15/01/2022	María Soledad Pastor	Version for DocEnhance partners' review
0.1	15/01/2022	Lena Korsnes	Minor edits

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1. MAIN EVALUATION OUTCOMES FROM BREAK-OUT GROUP DISCUSSIONS

General satisfaction with course design, structure and content

Positive feedback was received from participants in the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop (SEW) regarding the design, structure and content of the three DocEnhance pilot courses under evaluation: Supervision, Data Stewardship, and Career Management and Entrepreneurship.

Suggestions for course improvement

While participants did not mention any aspects of the courses as unnecessary, they did point out areas of improvement with regards to the course curriculum, in particular the need or convenience of including or further developing content on:

- Supervision course
 - o Online/digital supervision
 - o Wellbeing of both doctoral candidates and supervisors
 - o Rights and obligations of supervisors
 - o Good practices in supervision (for example, informal interdisciplinary discussion forums on supervision organised at the faculty level)

- Data Stewardship course
 - o Data management and data handling skills needed outside academia / research ethics and integrity
 - o Trustworthy software
 - o Data standardisation and data formats
 - o Implications in terms of data management when considering to develop research into business (i.e. core issues related to entrepreneurship)

- Career Management and Entrepreneurship course
 - o General soft skills (negotiation, communication, team work and team management, critical thinking, flexibility, networking ...)
 - o (Hard) business skills (funding, business terminology, patents, financing skills, business plan, policies and protocols, NDA, sales, basic legal notions ...)
 - o (Soft) business skills (business culture – values, dynamics, organisational structures and charts, processes and stereotypes, time management)
 - o Personal/life skills (self-assessment tools, self-awareness, mindfulness ...)
 - o Emotional intelligence (focus on how to work better in a team, for instance, how to be a better team player or how to be a better team leader)
 - o Professional mobility (moving between sectors and workplaces)

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Participants in the different break-out group discussions coincided in calling for a more interactive and/or experiential approach to the courses.

1.2. MAIN EVALUATION OUTCOMES FROM POST-WORKSHOP QUESTIONNAIRES

General satisfaction with stakeholder evaluation workshop and DocEnhance platform

Positive feedback was received from participants in the SEW regarding the workshop itself and the DocEnhance platform in particular. Participants especially valued their interest and usefulness.

The different aspects of the workshop were rated to be between very good and excellent, with the highest ratings going to moderators' knowledge of the subject, communication and interaction with participants, interest of the topics addressed, and interest and usefulness of the workshop.

With respect to the DocEnhance platform, respondents reported to be satisfied with the majority of the aspects assessed. The level of satisfaction was slightly lower when referred to graphic design, instantly comprehensible information, and satisfaction when searching for information.

Suggestions for improvement

Suggestions for future stakeholder workshops included diving deeper into how to improve job searching skills and transferable skills for researchers and how to improve/monitor the relationship between doctoral candidates and their supervisors. One respondent thought it would be enriching if PhDs working in industry were invited to participate and to share their experiences on what they needed to be hired and to perform as expected by industry. Another respondent pointed out that some stakeholders had problems accessing the courses online before the workshop and that perhaps a sample video could have been selected and sent to workshop participants in advance of the workshop.

Regarding the DocEnhance Platform, several respondents called for a forum for learners and teachers to post questions and comments, and to interact. One respondent mentioned that a course on research integrity would also be useful to PhD candidates and researchers in general. Both suggestions were also made during the break-out group discussions.

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2. INTRODUCTION

On September 13th 2021, the DocEnhance consortium celebrated the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop (SEW), in the frame of the [EUA-CDE](#) Annual Meeting, with the double objective of:

- presenting the first prototype of the DocEnhance Platform and its contents (the three transferable skills courses designed and piloted by different consortium members on Supervision, Data Management, and Career Management and Entrepreneurship) to interested stakeholders, and
- collecting vital external feedback and suggestions regarding its usefulness, usability and possible areas of improvement.

19 external stakeholders and 20 project partners' staff members from 12 countries participated in the SEW: Belgium (1), Finland (3), France (4), Germany (1), Greece (2), Ireland (1), Luxembourg (1), Norway (8), Portugal (1), Slovakia (2), Spain (13), and Sweden (1).

The institutional profile of external participants was varied: university (60%), business sector (30%), research centre (5%), and NGO (5%).

Participants' professional profile was also diverse, including for example: PhD candidate, PhD supervisor, doctoral school or programme staff, research associate, full professor, entrepreneurship coach, project manager, human resources manager.

The workshop was held online (via zoom) with the following agenda:

- 10:00-10:05 Welcome
Alexander Hasgall, Head of the EUA Council for Doctoral Education and DocEnhance External Advisor
- 10:05-10:10 The DocEnhance project
Hanne Risan Johnsen, DocEnhance Project Coordinator (UIT)
- 10:10-10:20 The DocEnhance Platform: a brief overview
Fabiana Minneci (EUF)
Evangelos Chondrokostas (AUPh)
- 10:20-11:30 Stakeholder discussions

Break-out group 1: Supervision Course

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Moderators: Virve Kallioniemi-Chambers (TAU) and Kamila Borsekova (UMB)

Break-out group 2: Data Stewardship Course
Moderators: James Lees (KAU) and Leif Longva (UIT)

Break-out group 3: Career Management and Entrepreneurship Course
Moderators: Elsa Caetano (UNL) and María Soledad Pastor (FUE)

11:30-12:00 Preliminary conclusions by Moderators

Break-out group moderators, together with the DocEnhance coordinator and WP leaders, agreed upon a common set of questions to be posed to participants in order to facilitate and dynamise the group discussions:

- What is your vision for a course on Data Stewardship/Career Management and Entrepreneurship/Supervision?
- How does the concept of the DocEnhance course fit to this vision?
- What learning outcomes should be expected from this course?
- Do you think that the course design, contents, methodology, learning materials and guidelines facilitate the expected learning outcomes?
- When you look at the curriculum, is there anything you feel is missing?
- Is there anything you consider superfluous?
- How can we improve these aspects of the course?

It was agreed that more specific questions would be made in line with participant profiles in each break-out group.

Prior to the SEW celebration, registered participants received an informed consent form (See Annex I) which included an information sheet on the workshop and a certificate of consent, to be signed by those planning to participate in the session.

They also received a pre-workshop information package (see Annex II) including a brief overview of the DocEnhance project and workshop objectives, a summary of the DocEnhance transferable skills courses, and instructions on how to register and log into the DocEnhance platform in order to facilitate their knowledge of the platform and its contents, and to ensure a fluid and dynamic discussion during the session.

After the SEW, which was recorded, and in order to complement the information gathered during the workshop discussions, the 19 external stakeholders participating in the workshop were invited to complete two brief questionnaires (see Annex III) on 1) different aspects of the workshop organization, content and development and 2) the DocEnhance Platform. The collection of data was carried out online (Google Forms) and the responses

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collected were anonymous. 36,8% completed the questionnaire on the platform and 31,6% responded to the questionnaire on the workshop itself.

The SEW questionnaire was provided by Fundación Universidad-Empresa, responsible for the workshop organization, while the questionnaire on the DocEnhance platform was produced by Universidade Nova de Lisboa, responsible for the platform development. Both were distributed to partners involved in the course design and piloting, work package leaders and DocEnhance coordinator for their review, comments and suggestions.

The questionnaires were organised in a given set of close-ended and open-ended questions.

The response options for a closed-ended question were exhaustive and mutually exclusive. The types of response for closed-ended questions are rate scale responses presented with a continuous scale based on 5 levels and referred to:

- Workshop: practical organisation of the workshop; moderators; workshop content and development; interest and usefulness of the workshop: and level of satisfaction.
- DocEnhance Platform: readability; navigation; search engine; graphic design; loading speed; and level of satisfaction.

Open-ended questions ask respondents to formulate his/her own answer in his/her own words, including comments and/or suggestions for improvement, referring to:

- Workshop: most and least interesting topics addressed; additional topics for inclusion in future stakeholder workshops; and usefulness.
- DocEnhance Platform: functionalities and usefulness.

Feedback gathered from the SEW discussions and questionnaires, together with the evaluation of the first implementation of the pilot courses will be taken into consideration when refining the course concept and content for the second round, foreseen for spring 2022, as well as for further development of the DocEnhance platform.

3. FEEDBACK FROM BREAK-OUT GROUP DISCUSSIONS

Qualitative results are presented separately for each course based on the notes taken by the break-out group moderators during the group discussions, as well as the session recordings.

3.1. BREAK-OUT GROUP 1: SUPERVISION

The general questions initially agreed to be used in the workshop, were not taken up systematically in the break-out group, but the discussion provided some valuable thoughts in relation to said questions, in particular:

- What is your vision for a course on Supervision?

The discussion confirmed that there is a clear need for universities to offer open educational resources in the field of doctoral supervision. Participants pointed out that while some universities already have some training in this area, many do not have anything at all. In the case of those universities that already offer some training in supervision, participants believed that they could benefit from the resources developed within the DocEnhance project.

- How does the concept of the DocEnhance course fit to this vision?

At the beginning of the break-out group discussion moderators pointed out that the pilot course on Supervision available on the DocEnhance platform should be considered to be more like a resource bank than closed course material designed to be implemented, for example, linearly following the content order. This approach was supported by participants in the break-out group.

- What learning outcomes should be expected from this course?

This question was not discussed in much detail, although it was clear for all participants that the topic – supervision – is very broad and that the open resources currently offered in the pilot course do not cover everything related to this activity.

- Do you think that the course design, (contents, methodology, learning materials and guidelines) facilitate the expected learning outcomes?

The course design received positive feedback from participants, although they pointed out that it is essential to include clear guidelines on the DocEnhance platform with information/instructions on how to use the material for different target groups (for example, junior or senior supervisors).

- When you look at the curriculum, is there anything you feel is missing? Is there anything you consider it is not needed? How can we improve these aspects of the course?

While participants did not mention any aspects of the course as unnecessary, they did point out several areas of improvement with regards to the course curriculum, in particular the need or convenience of including content on:

- online/digital supervision
- wellbeing of both doctoral candidates and supervisors
- rights and obligations of supervisors
- good practices in supervision (for example, informal interdisciplinary discussion forums on supervision organised at the faculty level)
- more interaction with students

Participants also mentioned that available documents from some universities regarding the duties and rights of doctoral candidates and supervisors could be checked. Based on these documents, the DocEnhance platform could include a document listing suggested topics to be covered in the supervision training schemes offered by different universities.

3.2. BREAK-GROUP 2: DATA STEWARDSHIP

To the extent that participants had the chance to look into the course, the feedback was positive regarding its design, structure and content.

There was a general consensus among participants that research data skills – in particular how to handle sensitive data - have become increasingly important in times of electronic research tools and data availability (including big data). They also addressed the growing link between good research data management and research integrity.

In this context, and considering that most participants in the break-out group with a PhD degree had received little or no training in Data Stewardship during their doctoral training, participants recommended that the Data Stewardship course be taken by all PhD candidates before entering the data collecting phase, irrespective of their position inside or outside academia.

They also suggested that the course should be promoted among doctoral supervisors or that a basic module be designed for supervisors and professors, as they considered that supervisors also need to master and/or update their own data stewardship skills. Experience from the University of Karlstad, when running the pilot, was that the course was useful to many different categories of participants, including supervisors.

Participants also suggested that the course could be more relevant and interesting to students from the humanities and social sciences areas if separate groups were set up for STEM and HSS subject backgrounds.

It was pointed out that Module 1 includes contact information with the course developers at UiT and that these contacts could be used as a “help desk” for local course organisers.

Regarding course methodology, participants in the break-out group considered that an interactive section should be made available, where students could communicate with local tutors and staff in order to resolve possible questions/doubts, as well as with peers in an open discussion forum on selected issues relevant to the course. It was also suggested that students should be brought together before the start of the course (for example via Slack) to facilitate the establishment of a strong cohort.

Participants addressed the following issues regarding course content:

- Data management and data handling skills needed outside academia / research ethics and integrity. An important issue raised by participants from the private industry sector referred to the privacy and security of their data. Data may be business sensitive and secrecy has to do with their competitive ability. This is a core issue when designing contracts between the university and private business and represents, to some extent, a culture clash with research, where openness and transparency are highly valued. In order to properly transmit how and what kind of data is handled and what data stewardship skills are needed outside academia, some participants suggested that students carry out assignments in cooperation with the non-academic sector (business, industry, public sector, etc.) in Module 3.
- What software is safe to use, in terms of privacy and security, when carrying out, for example, online questionnaire surveys or interviews? Some participants believed that the importance of trustworthy software was not sufficiently covered in the course.
- Data standardisation and data formats.
- Entrepreneurship. Some participants considered that the course should include some basic information on entrepreneurship for those students who want to transfer the work developed in the lab to the business sector. Moderators pointed out that entrepreneurship is covered in a different DocEnhance course, but that it could be possible to mention some core issues to consider in developing a research into business, and the implications in terms of data management, in the Data Stewardship course.

At any rate, the question regarding the level of detail to be expected from the course – i.e. how deeply should the course dig in to each topic – was raised. It was agreed that the

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course should aim principally at making students familiar with the concept of data stewardship and providing basic knowledge of data management terminology and the data management plan. Other resources should be made available for further more specific training.

BREAK-OUT GROUP 3: CAREER MANAGEMENT AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

The content of the Career Management and Entrepreneurship course was considered to be relevant. While nothing was considered superfluous, participants addressed the need to add or improve some contents.

Hence, the following skills could be better or more extensively integrated into the course:

- general soft skills (negotiation, communication, team work and team management, critical thinking, flexibility, networking ...)
- (hard) business skills (funding, business terminology, patents, financing skills, business plan, policies and protocols, NDA, sales, basic legal notions ...)
- (soft) business skills (business culture – values, dynamics, organisational structures and charts, processes and stereotypes, time management)
- personal/life skills (self-assessment tools, self-awareness, mindfulness ...)
- emotional intelligence (focus on how to work better in a team, for instance, how to be a better team player or how to be a better team leader)
- professional mobility (moving between sectors and workplaces)

On another hand, and in relation to the existing gap between universities and industry, participants called for a more experiential approach in the mobility module in order to clearly identify the differences between working in the academic or non-academic sectors. to improve the exchange of perspectives between both sectors, and to promote technology transfer carried out by PhDs. In this sense, participants shared some ideas that could be applied to the course's mobility module, i.e.:

- mentorship (company mentors and tutors)
- short job shadowing schemes
- networking opportunities (seminar/workshop with private actors, access to [PhDHub](#), alumni networks, ...)
- business virtual tours (videos)

Participants also suggested the existence of a Competence Framework for PhDs, similar to [EntreComp](#), [DigComp](#) or [LifeComp](#) but adapted to PhDs' needs and challenges.

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4. FEEDBACK FROM POST-WORKSHOP QUESTIONNAIRES

As already mentioned above in the INTRODUCTION, external stakeholders participating in the workshop discussions were invited to complete two brief questionnaires on different aspects of the workshop (organization, moderators, content and development, interest and usefulness, level of satisfaction) and the DocEnhance Platform (readability, navigation, search engine, graphic design, loading speed, functionalities, usefulness, and level of satisfaction).

36,8% of participating external stakeholders completed the questionnaire on the platform and 31,6% responded to the questionnaire on the workshop itself.

4.1. WORKSHOP QUESTIONNAIRE

Participants were asked to mark the rating that best reflected their opinion on each of the aspects to be assessed. The ratings were on a scale of 1 to 5 (1: very poor, 2: poor; 3: good; 4: very good; 5: excellent).

In general, the different aspects of the workshop were rated to be between very good and excellent. None of the aspects received a rating of poor or very poor. The highest ratings went to moderators' knowledge of the subject (4,67), communication and interaction with participants (4,50), interest of the topics addressed (4,50), and interest and usefulness of the workshop (4,50).

Formal Aspects	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
Workshop organisation	0,0%	0,0%	16,7%	33,3%	50,0%	4,33
Online connection	0,0%	0,0%	16,7%	33,3%	50,0%	4,33
Programme compliance	0,0%	0,0%	33,3%	16,7%	50,0%	4,17
Total	0,0%	0,0%	22,2%	27,8%	50,0%	4,28

Moderators	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
Communication / interaction with participants	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	50,0%	50,0%	4,50
Amenity of the presentations	0,0%	0,0%	16,7%	50,0%	33,3%	4,17
Knowledge of the subject	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	33,3%	66,7%	4,67
Total	0,0%	0,0%	5,6%	44,4%	50,0%	4,44

Content and Development	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
Duration	0,0%	0,0%	16,7%	50,0%	33,3%	4,17
Usefulness of topics addressed	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	66,7%	33,3%	4,33
Interest of topics addressed	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	50,0%	50,0%	4,50
Clarity and quality of contents	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	83,3%	16,7%	4,17
Interactive discussions	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	66,7%	33,3%	4,33
Total	0,0%	0,0%	3,3%	63,4%	33,3%	4,30

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Other Aspects	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
Interest and usefulness of the Workshop	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	50,0%	50,0%	4,50
Level of personal satisfaction	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	66,7%	33,3%	4,33
Total	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	58,3%	41,6%	4,42

When asked to identify the most interesting topics addressed in the workshop, respondents mentioned the opportunity of getting to know the PhD's perspective on their training needs, the need to include business and social/personal skills in PhD's transversal skills training, and the importance of data stewardship with respect to privacy and safety issues.

One respondent pointed out that some stakeholders had problems accessing the courses online before the workshop and that perhaps a sample video could have been selected and sent to workshop participants in advance of the workshop.

Suggestions for future stakeholder workshops included diving deeper into how to improve job searching skills and transferable skills for researchers, and how to improve/monitor the relationship between doctoral candidates and their supervisors, as well as to invite PhDs working in industry to share their experiences on what they needed to be hired and to perform as expected by industry.

4.2. PLATFORM QUESTIONNAIRE

Participants were asked to mark the rating that best reflected their opinion on each of the aspects to be assessed. The ratings were on a scale of 1 to 5 (1: very dissatisfied, 2: dissatisfied; 3: enough satisfied; 4: satisfied; 5: very satisfied).

In general, respondents reported to be satisfied (4,00) with the majority of the aspects assessed. The lowest ratings (between enough satisfied and satisfied) were given to: satisfaction when searching for information (3,86), instantly comprehensible information (3,43), and graphic design (3,43).

	1	2	3	4	5	Global score
To what extent is the Platform's content readable and viewable for you?	0,0%	0,0%	14,3%	71,4%	14,3%	4,00
To what degree do you consider the information comprehensible instantly?	0,0%	14,3%	28,6%	57,1%	0,0%	3,43
Qualify your level of satisfaction when searching for any kind of information.	0,0%	0,0%	28,6%	57,1%	14,3%	3,86
To what degree is the navigation simple and comprehensible?	0,0%	14,3%	0,0%	57,1%	28,6%	4,00
How much does the graphic design fulfil your expectations or meet your requirements?	14,3%	0,0%	28,6%	42,8%	14,3%	3,43
Evaluate the speed by which the elements are loaded	0,0%	14,3%	0,0%	57,1%	28,6%	4,00
Level of general satisfaction	0,0%	0,0%	14,3%	71,4%	14,3%	4,00
Total	2,0%	6,1%	16,3%	59,3%	16,3%	3,81

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When asked if they would include/exclude/edit any functionality to the DocEnhance Platform, several respondents called for a forum for learners and teachers to post questions and comments, and to interact. One respondent mentioned that a course on research integrity would also be useful to PhD candidates and researchers in general. Both suggestions were also made during the break-out group discussions.

With regards to the usefulness of the DocEnhance Platform for the respondents' sectors or institutions, they unanimously applauded the initiative, pointing out that:

- open educational resources are very important for the quality of doctoral (and postgraduate) education in Europe
- it is extremely useful for academics, considering the free tools and networking opportunities provided
- the resources offered can be used in many ways
- it can fill gaps in PhD student development and help them become ready for the workforce outside of academia
- it offers a semi-structured and adaptable online course, dealing with 3 fundamental topics

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5. ANNEX I: INFORMED CONSENT FORM

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This informed consent form is for stakeholders, who are invited to participate in the DocEnhance Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop organized by Fundación Universidad-Empresa.

Name of Organization: Fundación Universidad-Empresa
Name of Contact Person: Marisol Pastor
Name of Project: DocEnhance GA872483 H2020-SwafS-2019-1

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the workshop with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you choose to participate)

You will be given a copy of the full Informed Consent Form

Part I: Information Sheet

Introduction
 The DocEnhance project aims to enhance skills intelligence and integration into existing PhD programmes in Europe, and to increase interaction and exposure to the non-academic sector. To achieve this, the project is developing a series of transferable skills courses, a recommended PhD curriculum for Higher Education Institutions, and an online platform.

Information on the DocEnhance project is available on <https://docenhance.eu/>

Fundación Universidad-Empresa is involved in the DocEnhance project and as part of this project we would like to give you information on the Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop we are organizing as an online event scheduled for September 13th, 2021. If you have questions about the workshop, you can write to us at docenhance_cde-workshop@fue.es

Purpose of the workshop
 The workshop will present the first prototype of the DocEnhance Platform and its contents to interested stakeholders, with the objective of collecting vital feedback and suggestions regarding its usefulness, usability and possible areas of improvement.

Participants will receive relevant information for their evaluation before the workshop in order to ensure a fluid and dynamic discussion during the workshop.

Workshop Development

- A. This workshop consists of small group discussions. Your participation will help us to provide a useful platform where academic and non-academic actors may have the opportunity to connect and access the different resources (course, guidelines, reports and studies) created through the project. In this way you will contribute to improving and enhancing doctoral training in Europe and beyond.
- B. The workshop discussions will be recorded to facilitate the elaboration of recommendations and conclusions.
- C. After the workshop, you will be invited to fill out an evaluation questionnaire by Fundación Universidad-Empresa. The questionnaire is to be filled out online and the questions asked will concern different aspects of the workshop organization, content and development. You will also receive a questionnaire regarding the DocEnhance Platform.

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Recorte rectangular

Duration

The workshop will be held online on September 13th, 2021, from 10:00 to 12:00 CET.

Risks

The workshop and evaluation questionnaire will not address any sensitive information (e.g. political opinions or community beliefs) and the confidentiality arrangements in place will guarantee that any potentially identifying data collected (e.g. e-mail) will be anonymized before the elaboration of workshop recommendations and conclusions.

Reimbursements

This is an online workshop without direct costs to you. You will therefore not receive any monetary reimbursement for your participation.

Confidentiality

Fundación Universidad-Empresa will receive your contact information (e-mail) from the workshop registration form. The contact information provided will only be used for the purposes of DocEnhance workshop organization and follow-up. The evaluation questionnaire will be anonymous and will not seek any personally identifiable information.

Sharing the Results

The knowledge that we gain from this workshop will be shared with you and will also be made available to the public, including via the DocEnhance website. Each participant will receive a summary of the workshop conclusions.

Who to Contact

If you have any questions about this workshop, please contact Fundación Universidad-Empresa at docenhance.cde-workshop@fue.es

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European Commission

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Part II: Certificate of Consent

I have been invited to participate in the Docenhance Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop and am participating in this event to contribute to enabling higher education institutions to adjust their curricula with relevant and up-to-date skills.

I have read the foregoing information. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this workshop.

Print name of participant _____

Signature of participant _____

Date _____
Day/month/year

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this ICF has been provided to the participant.

Print name of organizer taking the consent _____

Signature of organizer taking the consent _____

Date _____
Day/month/year

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6. ANNEX II: PRE-WORKSHOP INFORMATION PACKAGE

PRE-WORKSHOP INFORMATION FOR PARTICIPANTS 13 September 2021

The DocEnhance project

DocEnhance is a three-year project (January 2020 - December 2022) funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme and aims to enhance transferable skills intelligence and integration into existing PhD programmes by:

- developing an employment and innovation-oriented curriculum for PhD programmes,
- facilitating business-education partnerships,
- tracking PhD graduate career paths.

The major outputs of the project are:

- a recommended transferable skills curriculum for PhD programmes,
- a new course concept and material,
- an open access career-tracking survey.

These outputs will be provided as Open Educational Resources (OER) through an online platform, the DocEnhance Platform (DEP).

For more information, please visit the [DocEnhance website](#).

About the workshop

The DocEnhance Stakeholder Evaluation Workshop will be held online on Monday 13th September 2021, from 10:00 to 12:00 CET. It will bring together international academic and non-academic actors in the frame of the [EUA-CDE Annual Meeting](#).

It provides an opportunity to present the work carried out so far by the consortium, discuss the main outcomes and ask for your feedback on how to improve them.

Main focus

Concretely, during the workshop, the first version of the DocEnhance Platform (DEP) will be presented to you as well as the content of the three courses: (I) PhD Supervision, (II) Data Stewardship, (III) Career management and Entrepreneurship.

To better prepare for our discussion during the workshop and ensure your active involvement, we have prepared the short information guide that follows.

We hope this information will be helpful!

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INFORMATION GUIDE

Transferable skills courses

The project focuses on transferable skills, as these skills facilitate the transition into employment and are widely applicable, regardless of the scientific field and chosen career path. The following transferable skills pilot courses are being created:

Course in Data Stewardship

As research data becomes more openly available, data stewardship is a skill in high demand, both within and beyond academia. DocEnhance provides a course for PhDs to master theory and concepts of data management, and to learn how to collect, analyse and manage research data. This theoretical course is completed with hands-on digital skills training, and on-site practical assignments in non-academic settings.

Course in Supervision

The quality of supervision is one of the most important factors in a successful PhD graduation. This affects not only the quality and content of the research output but also the completion rate, time to completion, student satisfaction, mental health, and future career prospects.

DocEnhance provides a course for supervisors and trainers to (1) Identify and embed pedagogical, practical and up-to-date skills in supervision, (2) know how to implement them in context, (3) master up-to-date research skills elements, (4) discover peer supervision, (5) adapt supervision practices.

Course in Career Management and Entrepreneurship

Research careers are rarely a single, predetermined path. A successful career involves being prepared to deviate from previous paths and explore entirely new options, and this does not always come readily. An under-exploited career path is entrepreneurship, requiring specific competencies.

DocEnhance provides a course for PhDs to learn how to: (1) reflect upon personal strengths, weaknesses and life goals, (2) develop critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication and self-management skills, (3) act upon entrepreneurial ideas and opportunities and transform them into value by mobilising resources and networks.

More information on the courses at <https://docenhance.eu>.

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The DocEnhance Platform (DEP)

The three above-mentioned courses and all DocEnhance Open Education Resources will be hosted in the [DocEnhance Platform](#), designed to provide an interdisciplinary space for cooperation and information sharing with the aim of supporting innovative career-oriented PhD training. It will provide academic and non-academic actors with the opportunity to connect and access the different resources (courses, guidelines, reports and studies) created through the project.

Watch the video to know more about the platform! Click [here](#).

Please kindly note that improvements over the first release of the platform and courses will be made during the project lifetime.

Registration and log-in

Please make sure to [complete the login process before the workshop](#), following the steps below.

1. The first step is to visit the DocEnhance Platform at <https://courses.docenhance.eu/>.
2. Click the 'Log in' button, in the top right corner.
3. To use the DocEnhance platform's full functionality, you will need to create an account on PhD Hub. Please choose the 'login with PhDHub' option.
4. By clicking on 'login with PhDHub' you will be redirected to the PhD Hub login (<https://phdhub.eu/login/>). Click on 'You don't have an account? Create one now!'
5. Fill in the registration form at <https://phdhub.eu/register/>. You can choose to create an account using your personal or institutional email. Please note that this step is only required to perform once.
6. Once you are registered, activate your account via the link sent to your email address.
7. Congratulations! Now that the registration process has been completed, you can log in to the DocEnhance Platform at <https://courses.docenhance.eu/login/>. Please remember to choose the 'login with PhDHub' option.

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7. ANNEX III: EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRES

7.1. DOCENHANCE STAKEHOLDER EVALUATION WORKSHOP EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is designed to obtain your opinion on the Workshop in which you have participated, in order to evaluate its quality and identify possible areas of improvement.

Please mark with an X the rating that best reflects your opinion on each of the aspects to be assessed (1: very poor, 5: excellent).

Thank you for your collaboration.

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Poor	Very poor
FORMAL ASPECTS					
Organisation	5	4	3	2	1
Quality of the online connection	5	4	3	2	1
Programme compliance	5	4	3	2	1
MODERATORS					
Communication / interaction with participants	5	4	3	2	1
Amenity of the presentations	5	4	3	2	1
Knowledge of the subject	5	4	3	2	1
CONTENT AND DEVELOPMENT					
Duration	5	4	3	2	1
Interest of topics addressed					
Usefulness of topics addressed	5	4	3	2	1
Clarity and quality of contents	5	4	3	2	1
Interactive discussions	5	4	3	2	1
OTHER ASPECTS					
Interest and usefulness of the Workshop	5	4	3	2	1
Level of personal satisfaction	5	4	3	2	1

What were the most interesting topics addressed in the workshop? Why?

And the least interesting? Why?

Would you include any additional topics in future stakeholder workshops? If so, please specify.

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Are the workshop conclusions useful for your institution and sector? Why? Would you include/exclude/edit any functionality to the DocEnhance Platform? If so, please specify.

Comments/Suggestions

7.2. DOCENHANCE PLATFORM EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

DOCENHANCE STAKEHOLDER EVALUATION WORKSHOP SEPTEMBER 13, 2021

This questionnaire is designed to obtain your opinion on the DocEnhance Platform, in order to evaluate its quality and identify possible areas of improvement.

Please mark with an X the rating that best reflects your opinion on each of the aspects to be assessed (1: very dissatisfied, 5: very satisfied).

Thank you for your collaboration.

	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Enough satisfied	Dissatisfied	Very dissatisfied
Specify to what extent is the DocEnhance Platform's content readable and viewable for you.	5	4	3	2	1
To what degree do you consider the information comprehensible instantly?	5	4	3	2	1
Qualify your level of satisfaction when searching for any kind of information. <i>(It does not matter if you finally found what you were looking for).</i>	5	4	3	2	1
Specify to what degree is the navigation simple and comprehensible.	5	4	3	2	1
How much does the graphic design fulfil your expectations or meet your requirements?	5	4	3	2	1
Evaluate the speed by which the elements are loaded.	5	4	3	2	1
Level of general satisfaction.	5	4	3	2	1

Would you include/exclude/edit any functionality to the DocEnhance Platform? If so, please specify.

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Is the DocEnhance Platform useful for your sector or institution? Why?

Comments/Suggestions